

Investigation of Antioxidant Potentials of Methanolic and Ethyl Acetate Fractions of Tualang Honey

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ABSTRACT

Background: Many honey components, particularly the flavonoids and phenolic acids, have been shown to contribute significantly to the antioxidant capacity. However, when separated from honey and tested in *in vitro* systems, they produce only a portion of the total antioxidant activity of honey.

Objective: This study was conducted to investigate the antioxidant potentials of four different samples of Tualang honey i.e. non-irradiated Tualang honey (TH), gamma-irradiated Tualang honey (THI), methanolic fraction of Tualang honey (MTH) and ethyl acetate fraction of Tualang honey (EATH). The correlation between the antioxidant contents and antioxidant activities was also investigated.

Method: The antioxidant contents were determined by using Folin-Ciocalteu and UV-spectrophotometry methods. The antioxidant activities were determined using 2,2-Diphenyl, 2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging, 2,2'-Azinobis-(3-Ethylbenzthiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) and ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assays.

Conclusion: MTH exhibited the highest antioxidant potentials compared to TH, THI and EATH.

KEY WORDS

methanolic fraction of Tualang honey (MTH), ethyl acetate fraction of Tualang honey (EATH), total phenolic, total flavonoids, antioxidant activities

INTRODUCTION

Natural honey contains more than 300 constituents, but its main composition is sugars, primarily fructose and glucose, with small amounts of fructo-oligosaccharides¹⁻⁴⁾. The composition of honey varies, primarily depending on the floral source. However, certain external factors also play a role, such as seasonal and environmental factors and processing⁵⁾. It is notable that, irrespective of its floral source, honey contains phytochemicals, flavonoids, catalase, phenolic acids, ascorbic acid, antibiotic-rich inhibine, tocopherols, and peptides, and most of these substances work in synergy to provide its beneficial effects^{3,6-7)}. These effects are known as synergistic multiple ingredients factor or SMIF⁸⁾.

Generally, the antioxidant activity of honey is attributed to its phenolic and flavonoids compounds⁸⁻¹¹⁾. Its antioxidant properties have been shown to play an important role against various diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, inflammatory disorders, neurological degeneration, infectious diseases and aging¹²⁻¹⁴⁾. Free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) have been implicated in the processes of aging and various diseases¹⁵⁾. Humans protect themselves from these damaging compounds, in part, by absorbing antioxidants from high-antioxidant foods including honey. Schramm *et al.*¹⁵⁾ demonstrated that phenolic antioxidants from processed buckwheat honey are bioavailable, and they

increased plasma antioxidant activity. Thus, it is proposed that these compounds may augment body defenses against oxidative stress and that they may protect humans from oxidative stress¹⁶⁾.

Studies on the antioxidant activity of different types of honey from different countries and different botanical origins have been carried out¹⁷⁻²¹⁾. In addition, comparison studies of the antioxidant activity between Malaysian honey and honey from other countries as well as among Malaysian honey have also been reported. However, comparison studies of the main antioxidant contents and activities between different types of Tualang honey fraction are still lacking.

Many honey components, particularly the flavonoids and phenolic acids, have been shown to contribute significantly to the antioxidant capacity. However, when separated from honey and tested in *in vitro* systems, they produce only a portion of the total antioxidant activity of honey. These results led to the conclusion that several antioxidants may act synergistically in honey²²⁾ and support the SMIF effects of honey. An earlier study by Mohamad Shah *et al.*²³⁾ reported that the methanolic fraction of Tualang honey (MTH) has a positive anti-proliferative effect on keloid fibroblasts in a dose-dependent manner but could not exclude the possible beneficial effect of using a less polar solvent such as petroleum spirit, hexane or ethyl acetate. Another study reported that ethyl acetate fraction of Tualang honey (EATH) had better antioxidant capacity compared to MTH²⁴⁾. Thus, this study aims to investigate the antioxidant contents and activities of Tualang honey (TH), gamma-irradiated

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Figure 1. Main steps for the fractionation of honey sample using C18 solid-phase extraction cartridges

Table 1. Total Phenolic and Flavonoid contents of four Tualang honey samples

	Total Phenolic (mg GAE/100 g)	Total Flavonoid (mg CEQ/100 g)
TH	5.75 ± 0.08	1.35 ± 0.12
THI	7.52 ± 0.05	1.37 ± 0.08
MTH	287.80 ± 0.85***	189.53 ± 1.23***
EATH	46.93 ± 0.13***	26.15 ± 1.49**

TH - Tualang honey, THI - Tualang honey irradiated, MTH - methanolic fraction of Tualang honey, EATH - ethyl acetate fraction Tualang honey, mg GAE/100 g - mg gallic acid equivalents, mg CEQ/100 g - mg catechin equivalents. Values are expressed as the mean ± standard deviation from three independent experiments (n = 3). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 vs. TH group.

Table 3: Correlations between antioxidant contents and antioxidant activities of combined honey samples

	DPPH	FRAP	ABTS
TPC	-0.612	0.690	0.866
	p = 0.034	p = 0.013	p < 0.001
TFC	-0.602	0.681	0.860
	p = 0.038	p = 0.015	p < 0.001

TPC - Total phenolic content, TFC - total flavonoid content, DPPH - 2,2-Diphenyl, 2-picrylhydrazyl, FRAP - Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power, ABTS - 2,2'-Azinobis-(3-Ethylbenzthiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) diammonium salt. Values are expressed as Pearson correlation coefficient, r. p < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Tualang honey (THI), MTH and EATH. This study also aims to validate the correlation between the antioxidant contents and activities of these samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tualang honey samples

Tualang honey was used from a single batch honey supplied by

Table 2: IC50 of DPPH, FRAP and ABTS values of four Tualang honey samples

	IC50 of DPPH (mg/ml)	FRAP (mmol Fe(II)/mg)	ABTS (mmol TE/g)
TH	71.27 ± 2.42	2.90 ± 0.15	13.22 ± 1.92
THI	31.13 ± 1.20*	3.34 ± 0.85	13.97 ± 2.82
MTH	1.42 ± 0.27***	37.56 ± 4.60*	135.34 ± 7.60***
EATH	3.25 ± 0.42***	36.66 ± 5.24*	91.57 ± 10.37***

TH - Tualang honey, THI - Tualang honey irradiated, MTH - methanolic fraction of Tualang honey, EATH - ethyl acetate fraction Tualang honey, DPPH - 2,2-Diphenyl, 2-picrylhydrazyl, FRAP - Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power, ABTS - 2,2'-Azinobis-(3-Ethylbenzthiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) diammonium salt. Values are expressed as the mean ± standard deviation from three independent experiments (n = 3). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 vs. TH group.

Federal Agricultural Marketing Authorities (FAMA), Malaysia. The honey was filtered by FAMA to remove any solid particles, concentrated in heat at 40°C and evaporated to achieve a water content of about 20%. It was then exposed to gamma (γ) irradiation at 25 kGy at Steril Gamma (M) Sdn. Bhd. (Selangor, Malaysia) for sterilization.

Fractionation of honey

The Tualang honey was subjected to solid-phase extraction (SPE) to fractionize phenolic compounds as earlier described by Kaškonienė *et al.*²⁵ with slight modifications. The honey samples were dissolved in five parts of acidified deionized water (pH 2 attained by using 2.0 M hydrochloric acid) until completely fluid and then filtered through cotton wool to remove solid particles. The solution was passed through preconditioned C18 cartridges (6 mL x 1 g). The cartridges were preconditioned by successively passing 6 mL each of methanol and acidified water. The aqueous honey solution was applied to the cartridge at a drop-wise flow rate to ensure efficient adsorption of phenolic compounds. The cartridges were then washed with acidified water to remove all sugars and other polar constituents of honey. Later, the adsorbed compounds were eluted with methanol and evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 40°C. The dried methanol fraction was divided into two portions. One portion was used as the methanolic fraction (MTH) and the second portion was re-dissolved in deionized water (1 ml) and re-fractionated with ethyl acetate (EATH). Figure 1 shows the main steps for the fractionation of honey sample using C18 solid-phase extraction cartridges.

Total Phenolic Content (TPC)

Phenolic compounds from honey samples were determined using Folin-Ciocalteu reagents as described by Tan *et al.*²⁶ with minor modifications. Briefly, 200 µl of honey (200 mg/ml) and honey fraction (0.5 mg/ml) were each well mixed with 1 ml Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 min. Then 1 ml of 10% sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) was added to the mixture and adjusted to 10 ml with distilled water. After incubation in the dark for 90 min, the absorbance of reaction mixture was measured at 725 nm by a UV/VIS spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used to obtain the standard curve (0.004-0.5 mg/ml; y = 0.0017x + 0.0359; R² = 0.9956). The mean of three analyses was obtained and the total phenolic content was expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE/100 g).

Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)

The total flavonoid content of each honey sample was determined spectrophotometrically by using a method as previously described by Khalil *et al.*¹⁰. Briefly, 200 µl of honey (200 mg/ml) and honey fraction (0.5 mg/ml) were each mixed with 4 ml of distilled water, followed by the addition of 0.3 ml of 5% sodium nitrite (NaNO₂) solution. After 5 min, 0.3 ml of 10% aluminium trichloride (10%) was added, followed by the addition of 2 ml of 1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 6 min later. The solution was adjusted to 10 ml by the addition of distilled water. The mixture was vigorously shaken and the absorbance was read at 510 nm by a UV/VIS spectrophotometer. Catechin was used as a standard to produce the calibration curve (0.004-0.5 mg/ml; y = 0.0003x + 0.01; R² = 0.9716). The mean of three analyses was obtained and the total flavonoid content was expressed as mg catechin equivalents (mg CEQ/100 g).

2,2-Diphenyl, 2-picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging

The DPPH radical scavenging activity was determined according to the method by Alves *et al.*²⁷⁾, with slight modifications. Briefly, 0.3 ml of various concentrations of honey (50 to 500 mg/ml) and honey fraction (0.5 to 5 mg/ml) were each mixed with 2.7 ml of methanolic solution containing DPPH radicals (0.024 mg/ml). The mixture was forcefully shaken and left in the dark for 15 minutes at room temperature (until their absorbance remained unchanged). The absorbance was measured at 517 nm and gallic was used as reference material. The radical scavenging activity was measured as the percentage of DPPH discoloration using the equation: % Inhibition = (Abs blank - Abs sample)/Abs blank x 100, where Abs blank is the blank absorbance at 517 nm and Abs sample is the sample absorbance at 517 nm. All experiments were carried out in triplicate. The results were expressed as IC50 and the graph was plotted to determine the IC50 of each sample and standard. IC50 is the effective concentration at which 50% of DPPH radicals were scavenged.

2.2.4.2 Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay

FRAP assay was performed according to a modified method described by Chua *et al.*²⁸⁾. The working solution of FRAP reagent must be freshly prepared by mixing 300 mM acetate buffer pH 3.6, 10 mM 2,4,6-tripyridyl-s-triazine (TPTZ) solution in 40 mM HCl and 20 mM FeCl₃·6H₂O in a 10:1:1 ratio and the reagent was warmed in a water bath at 37°C prior to using. Briefly, 200 µL of properly diluted honey (200 mg/ml) and honey fraction (0.5 mg/ml) were each dissolved with 1.8 mL of FRAP reagent. The absorbance of the reagent mixture was measured spectrophotometrically at 593 nm after incubation for 15 min in the dark condition at 37°C. All reactions were done in triplicate. A calibration curve was obtained, using an aqueous solution of ferrous sulfate (FeSO₄·7H₂O) at 100-1000 µmol/L ($y = 0.0003x + 2.43$; $R^2 = 0.9977$). The results were expressed in mmol Fe(II)/mg.

2,2'-Azinobis-(3-Ethylbenzthiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) diammonium salt (ABTS) assay

The improved method applied for ABTS radical scavenging activity was described by Annamaria *et al.*²⁹⁾. Briefly, a stock solution (50 ml) of ABTS (2 mM) was prepared in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), pH 7.4. The ABTS radical was produced by reacting 50 ml of ABTS stock solution with 200 µL potassium persulfate (K₂S₂O₈). The mixture was left in the dark at room temperature for 12-16 h before use. For the determination of antioxidant activity, 2 ml of ABTS+ solution was diluted in PBS until it reached an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.020 at 734 nm (blank). 100 µL of honey (200 mg/ml) and honey fraction (0.5 mg/ml) were each mixed with 2 mL of the final ABTS solution. After 10 min, the decrease in the absorbance was measured at 734 nm. All reactions were done in triplicate. Trolox was used as a standard to produce the calibration curve ($0.00-2.40$ mmol/L; $y = -0.0501x + 97.21$; $R^2 = 0.945$). The results were expressed in mmol TE/g.

Statistical analysis

All data were analysed using SPSS version 24.0 software and expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation ($n = 3$). The data were analysed using one-way ANOVA and Tukey's post-hoc test to determine the mean differences between four honey samples. Pearson's correlation coefficients test was used to identify relationships between antioxidant content and antioxidant activity. Differences were considered statistically significant at levels of $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The antioxidant contents and activities of four Tualang honey samples

The antioxidant contents and activities of four Tualang honey samples are shown in Tables 1 and 2. MTH exhibited the highest amount of total phenolic and flavonoids contents followed by EATH. Both MTH and EATH showed a higher amount of total phenolic and flavonoids contents compared to TH and THI. However, there were no significant differ-

ences in total phenolic and flavonoid contents between TH and THI.

The radical scavenging activities of the honey samples were analyzed using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl radicals (DPPH) and 2,2'-Azinobis-(3-Ethylbenzthiazoline-6-Sulphonic Acid) diammonium salt (ABTS). The MTH was found to have the lowest DPPH scavenging with IC50 (50% inhibitory concentration) value of 1.42 ± 0.27 followed by EATH (3.25 ± 0.42), THI (31.13 ± 1.20) and TH (71.27 ± 2.42). For ABTS assay, the values were higher in MTH and EATH compared to TH. There were no significant differences between TH and THI samples.

The FRAP assay measures the reducing potential of an antioxidant that reacts with a ferric tripyridyltriazine (Fe³⁺ - TPTZ) complex to produce a colored ferrous tripyridyltriazine (Fe²⁺ - TPTZ)^{30,31)}. There were significant higher FRAP values in MTH and EATH when compared to TH. Similar to ABTS assay, there were no significant differences of FRAP values between TH and THI.

Correlations between antioxidant contents and activities

The correlations between antioxidant contents (TPC and TFC) and antioxidant activities (DPPH, FRAP, ABTS) we analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient and the values are summarized in Table 3. A significant positive correlation was found between FRAP and ABTS values of honey samples with TPC ($r = 0.690$ and $r = 0.866$, respectively), as well as between TFC ($r = 0.681$, and $r = 0.860$, respectively). A significant negative correlation was found between DPPH scavenging with IC50 values of honey samples with TPC and TFC ($r = -0.612$, $r = -0.602$, respectively).

DISCUSSION

Most of the previous studies compare antioxidant properties of Malaysian honey produced by different bees³²⁾, with and without gamma irradiation³³⁾ or between Malaysian honey and honey from other countries^{10,11,34)}. Moniruzzaman *et al.*³²⁾ evaluated the antioxidant properties of Malaysian honey produced by different bees; *Apis cerana*, *Apis dorsata* and *Apis mellifera*. Acacia and pineapple honey are produced by *Apis mellifera* bees while Borneo and Tualang honey are produced by *Apis cerana* and *Apis dorsata* bees, respectively. They found that TH had the highest concentration of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, DPPH, FRAP values and protein content as well as the lowest AEAC values, indicating its strong antioxidant properties.

The results of the experiment in terms of antioxidant contents and activities oppose the trend suggested in the literature by researchers such as Hussein *et al.*³³⁾ and Khalil *et al.*³⁵⁾. Hussein *et al.*³³⁾ evaluated the antioxidant activities and total phenolic and flavonoid contents of two types of monofloral Malaysian honey (Gelam and Nenas), with and without gamma irradiation. They found that Gelam honey exhibited higher antioxidant activity ($p < 0.05$) than Nenas honey and both irradiated honey have higher antioxidant activities and total phenolic and flavonoid contents compared to nonirradiated honey. They concluded that irradiation of honey causes enhanced antioxidant activities and flavonoid compounds³³⁾.

A later study by Khalil *et al.*³⁵⁾ found irradiation and evaporation of Tualang honey resulted in high antioxidant potentials (FRAP) and maintained the total dissolved solid (TDS) and electrical conductivity (EC) within recommended levels. They proposed that irradiation-induced bond breakage in some glycosidic compounds in honey which results in the release of phenolic components that contribute to increased antioxidant activity³³⁾. Thus our results suggest that unlike Gelam and Nenas honey, Tualang honey should be evaporated and irradiated to enhance its antioxidant content.

However, our results are in contrast with a recent finding in which EATH had better antioxidant capacity than MTH²⁴⁾. Our results support the notion that more polar solvent i.e. methanol can concentrate flavonoids and phenolic compounds in the honey better than less polar solvent i.e. ethyl acetate³⁶⁾. The used of different techniques for extraction may not explain this discrepancy and warrant further studies.

The present study confirmed previous findings^{17,33)} on a significant positive correlation between antioxidant activities and antioxidant contents. Al-Mamary *et al.*¹⁷⁾ found positive correlation between percentage of antioxidant and total phenolics of five different types of Yemeni honey namely *Acacia ehrenbergina* (Salam-Tehamah), *Acacia edge-worhi* (Somar-Hadramout), *Ziziphus Spinachristi* L. (Sidr-Hadramout), *Ziziphus Spina-christi* L. (Sidr-Taiz), Tropical blossom (Marbai-Hadramout), and four types of imported origins namely an American-Tropical blossom (New Orleans), an American-Orange source (Florida),

Swiss-blossom, and an Iranian-Tropical blossom.

Hussien *et al.*³³⁾ also found a significant positive correlation between FRAP and DPPH values of Gelam and Nenas honey with TPC, as well as between total flavonoid content and antioxidant activity. Apart from these two studies, other studies have also found good correlations between antioxidant capacities and phenolic as well as flavonoid contents, indicating that the phenolics and flavonoids are one of the major components responsible for the antioxidant activity of honey^{3,37-38)}.

CONCLUSIONS

Our results indicate that among the four Tualang honey samples, MTH has the highest antioxidant contents and activities. We also confirm the positive correlations between antioxidant contents and antioxidant activities, suggesting the total phenolics and flavonoids are the major components responsible for the antioxidant activities of Tualang honey.

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